

TIP NOISE IN A COMPRESSOR CASCADE AT TWO OPERATING CONDITIONS

Marlène Sanjosé

Department of Aerospace Engineering
École de Technologie Supérieure
Montreal H3C1K3 QC Canada

Stéphane Moreau

Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Sherbrooke
Sherbrooke J1K2R1 QC Canada

ABSTRACT

The flow in a rectilinear compressor cascade with a tip was investigated at two operating conditions using incompressible SBES and compressible LES solvers. At best efficiency point (BEP) both accurately reproduced the aerodynamics observed in Virginia Tech Low Speed Wind Tunnel experiments, though they exhibited distinct dynamic behaviors in Spectral Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (SPOD) analysis. The SBES predicted coupled modes between the tip leakage vortex (TLV) and trailing-edge vortex shedding (VS), while the LES revealed uncoupled but pressure and suction side coupling via the tip leakage flow. This difference is attributed to the hybrid RANS-LES resolution in SBES, which amplifies natural instabilities. At the maximum pressure rise (MPR) condition, analyzed with SBES only, increased loading shifted the TLV burst upstream, and SPOD revealed strong coupling between the pressure and suction sides via a travelling mode along the pressure side. Far-field noise computed from the LES results at BEP identified three dominant sources, including a significant tip-gap noise contribution, larger around 1 kHz. These results highlight the influence of turbulence modeling on unsteady flow coupling and acoustic generation mechanisms in compressor cascades.

Keywords: compressor cascade, tip gap, aeroacoustics, LES, SBES, SPOD

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern turbofan engines exhibit a strong leakage flow created by the required tip clearance between rotating rows and fixed parts. The pressure difference between pressure and suction sides generates complex vortical structures [1] that interact with the main stream flow, producing substantial losses [2]. The tip-leakage flow is also responsible for stall inception and

noise emission because of the strong unsteady mechanisms involved [3]. Tip-leakage noise in modern turbofan engines is indeed becoming a significant noise contribution at take-off and approach regimes [4]. This complex flow is excessively difficult to measure [5] or to simulate [6]. Several numerical methods have been used to reproduce tip-leakage flows in academic or industrial configurations. Koch *et al.* [7], Boudet *et al.* [8], and Mann *et al.* [9] performed respectively a Large-Eddy Simulation (LES), a Zonal Large-Eddy Simulation (ZLES), and a Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) on a non-rotating isolated airfoil with tip gap in order to investigate the main noise source. The source is located on the airfoil tip, between midchord and the trailing edge, and radiates around 2 kHz and 6 kHz, with a stronger directivity on the pressure side, which is consistent with experimental investigations [10]. Then, Arroyo *et al.* [11] and Kholodov & Moreau [12] identified the noise sources in a modern turbofan with LES. The NASA Source Diagnostic Test (SDT) turbofan at approach regime exhibits two main noise sources: the blade self noise at the trailing edge and the tip noise. The latter appears to be the dominant noise source below 6 kHz. These observations were also in good agreement with experimental results [13, 14].

On the one hand, academic configurations such as isolated airfoils with tip gap allow studying separately the sound generation mechanisms related to the tip-leakage flow without the rotating or the cascade effects, while reducing the experimental costs on such simplified geometries. On the other hand, the full industrial configurations such as the NASA SDT turbofan take into account all the different mechanisms responsible for noise emissions, but the complexity of the geometry makes it very difficult to reproduce numerically. Thus, a linear compressor cascade can be seen as an intermediate configuration, which can be used to increase the number of flow mechanisms involved in a tip-leakage flow compared to an isolated airfoil, while keep-

ing a simple geometry to reduce the experimental and computational costs compared to the full industrial configuration. You *et al.* [15] have successfully performed an incompressible LES of a linear compressor cascade with tip gap (blade shape, a 4%-thick modified circular-arc section with a chord length of 254 mm, a stagger angle of 56.9° and a solidity of 1.08), to investigate the tip-clearance losses. Koch *et al.* [16] then used a compressible LES to analyze the aeroacoustic sources associated with the tip-leakage flow on this same compressor. Good agreement with experimental results at Virginia Tech University [17–19] was achieved by comparing the aerodynamic behavior of the tip-leakage flow. More recently, Becherucci *et al.* extended this work to a moving top wall to mimic the experiment more closely, and found a slight modification of the size and trajectory of the tip leakage vortex [20]. Given the large experimental database available on this configuration, it is an interesting configuration that serves for validation of numerical methods.

In this work, the influence of operating conditions on the tip gap flow and the associated noise sources are investigated.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Computational domain, boundary conditions and grid

The investigated rectilinear cascade geometry includes a single blade passage from the 7 passages that compose the experimental section of the Cascade Wind Tunnel operated at Virginia Tech (VT) [21]. The flow, in particular the wakes and the tip gap flow, was intensively characterized in several experimental campaigns at the BEP [22, 23]. The computational domain used in the simulations is shown in Fig. 1. It was first proposed by You *et al.* [24]. Its dimensions are $4C \times 1C \times 1.5C$ in the streamwise (X), spanwise (Y) and the transverse (Z) directions respectively. The total tunnel height is $H = 254$ mm which also corresponds to the chord $C = 254$ mm of the extruded blade. The tip gap height $h = 4$ mm corresponds to 1.6% of the chord. The lower wall mimics the casing wall in a turbomachine. It is located at the coordinate $Y = 0$ facing the tip of the blade. The blades are staggered with an angle $\chi = 57.1^\circ$ with respect to the streamwise direction X . The axial chord is defined as $C_a = C \cos \chi$. A dimensionless coordinate $x_c^* = (X - X_{LE}) \cos \chi - (Z - Z_{LE}) \sin \chi$ is defined to measure the position along the chord, with (X_{LE}, Z_{LE}) the coordinates of the leading-edge.

The boundary conditions are identified in Fig 1. Periodic conditions are applied in the transverse direction, whereas no-slip conditions are specified everywhere except on the upper wall where no shear is applied to simplify the resolution. The upstream velocity U_0 corresponds to the relative velocity of the flow as seen by the blade. The angle β_0 corresponds to the angle of the flow with respect to the machine direction (X).

In the present work, the velocity intensity is kept at $U_0 = 25.2$ m/s. Two configurations are considered with β_0 equals to

FIGURE 1. NUMERICAL DOMAIN USED FOR THE COMPUTATIONS.

65.1° and 69.1° , corresponding to an angle of attack of 8° and 12° with respect to the blade chord. These operating points were carefully selected to represent the Best Efficiency Point (BEP) and the Maximum Pressure Rise (MPR) of the compressor cascade respectively. The Reynolds number based on the blade chord is therefore identical in the two simulations at $Re_c = 4.4 \times 10^5$. The Mach number is $Ma = 0.07$. Standard air pressure and temperature conditions are considered. No turbulence is set at the inlet plane.

FIGURE 2. MESH.

Description of the grid in Fig. 2.

2.2 Numerical methods

In this work, two solvers that provide different levels of fidelity were used on the same domain and mesh grids. The ANSYS CFX solver 2023.R1 was used to perform incompressible Shear Blended Eddy Simulations (SBES), which is a recent hybrid RANS-LES approach that enforces a RANS resolution at the wall with varying mesh refinement and ensures a rapid transition to LES resolution in shear layers [25]. In the simulations, the fully-turbulent $k - \omega$ SST model was selected in combination with the WALE subgrid scale LES model [26]. The numerical solver is an Upwind Differencing Scheme with a numerical advection correction which tends towards a second order scheme but limiting dispersive errors in high gradient regions [27, 28]. An implicit dual-time step approach is used to solve the non-linear transport equations. A time step of 1.3×10^{-5} s ensured a maximum convective CFL number of 5 in the tip region of the blade, and only 3 inner linearization iterations per time step to reach a L2-norm residual target of 5×10^{-5} in the momentum equations. In addition, compressible LES simulations using AVBP V7.16, a massively parallel LES solver developed

by CERFACS [29], were performed on the same configuration at both operating conditions, leveraging recent works [16, 20]. In AVBP, the filtered Navier-Stokes equations are explicitly resolved using the two step Taylor-Galerkin TTG4A [30]. The WALE subgrid scale LES model is selected, and artificial viscosity are used to limit dispersion errors in high gradient regions. A time-step of 0.7×10^{-7} s ensured an acoustic CFL condition of 0.7 over the entire grid to limit the dissipative errors of TTG4A [31] for direct acoustic propagation in the computational domain. While in the SBES approach, the transition of the boundary layers was naturally captured by the fully turbulent $k - \omega$ SST model [32], in the LES approach, the transition was enforced on the suction side using a random tripping method [16] similarly as in the experiments [17, 21].

In this work in progress, given the computational resources required for the LES simulations, a converged state for the MPR condition was reached, but no statistics have been collected yet. The results will be presented during the congress only.

First, the aerodynamic results of the two solvers are analyzed at the best efficiency point and validated against the experiments. A Spectral Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (SPOD) recently popularized by Towne *et al* [33, 34], is performed to identify the driving dynamics of the tip leakage flow in the cascade configuration. The principle of this decomposition is to project the temporal evolution of the flow field onto an optimal spatio-temporal basis. The latter are defined as the eigenvectors of the cross-spectral density matrix at each frequency. For this analysis, the velocity component and the pressure are collected on identical surfaces as shown in Fig. 3. A Welch periodogram is first applied to define the frequency samples for POD analysis. In the SBES simulations, the time signal is divided into 15 blocks allowing an overlap of 80% between the blocks. In the LES simulations, the time signal is divided into 10 overlapping blocks, which is a compromise between frequency resolution and sample numbers for the analysis. A Hanning windowing and about 20% of zero padding are applied, before a fast Fourier transform is applied to each segment. The SPOD spectrum resolution is reported in Tab. 1. Modal decomposition is applied independently for each plane in Fig. 3.

3 AERODYNAMIC RESULTS AT BEST EFFICIENCY POINT

In this main section, the aerodynamic results obtained from the SBES-BEP and LES-BEP simulations are carefully analyzed and compared with the experimental database. A modal decomposition of the flow will identify the main dynamic mode in the configuration operating at Best Efficiency Point.

FIGURE 3. PLANES OF ANALYSIS FOR THE SPOD DECOMPOSITION.

FIGURE 4. INSTANTANEOUS VISUALIZATION USING AN ISOSURFACE OF Q CRITERION IN LES (TOP) AND SBES (BOTTOM).

3.1 Flow visualizations

An instantaneous visualization of the main flow structures is provided in Fig. 4 using an iso-surface of the second invariant of the velocity gradient $Q = 5 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-2}$. The tip gap flow allowed by the 1.6% C tip clearance in the configuration is clearly demonstrated by the large tip leakage vortex that is identified in the two configurations. Several main differences inherent to the numerical methods employed can be clearly identified. They are highlighted with a circled number. In the LES, the turbulent structures are resolved in the boundary layer ① that develops along the suction side after the tripping. The granularity of the random trip causes non-uniform streets of vortices in the initially accelerating boundary layer. The turbulence becomes uniform in the rear of the blade. On the pressure side, which can be visualised through transparency in region ①, a natural transition allows the

TABLE 1. SIMULATION SUMMARY.

Name	Flow Angle	Solver	Approach	Numerical Order	Statistics collected	SPOD Resolution
SBES-BEP	65.1°	ANSYS	SBES	< 2	8 T_c	40 Hz
SBES-MPR	69.1°	ANSYS	SBES	< 2	15 T_c	30 Hz
LES-BEP	65.1°	AVBP	LES	3	2 T_c	110 Hz
LES-MPR	69.1°	AVBP	LES	3	N/A	N/A

FIGURE 5. MEAN FLOW VISUALIZATION USING AN ISOSURFACE OF Q CRITERION IN LES (LEFT) AND SBES (RIGHT) COLORED BY THE HELICITY.

development of a more uniform turbulent boundary layer. Finally, the turbulent boundary layers gather in a turbulent wake in ② that rapidly dissipates as the mesh coarsens. In the SBES, no structure is visible along the boundary layer ① that is maintained in a RANS mode of resolution. In the wake ②, the von Kàrmàn instability develops and is captured by the LES mode. The tip gap region in the SBES shows coherent structures, in particular the strong coherent tip leakage vortex (TLV) surrounded by induced vortices in ③. This confirms that the hybrid approach switches to a LES mode in region ③. The vortex structures appear smaller in the SBES than in the LES, which is a direct consequence of the order of the numerical scheme employed. Similar structures as in the LES can be retrieved in the SBES simulation with a Q iso-surface of ten times lower value [35]. Finally, in region ④, turbulent eddies develop along the lower wall surface. This is caused by the blockage effect of the tip gap flow. The incoming flow is deviated towards the pressure side and sees a rapid pressure increase. The lower wall boundary layer thickens and larger turbulent structures are resolved. In the SBES, no turbulent structures can be identified in the lower wall region.

The tip gap flow is better analyzed in a close view of the tip edge of the blade in Fig. 5 using an isosurface $Q = 5 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-2}$ computed from the gradients of the time averaged velocity field. The isosurface is colored by the helicity that corresponds to the mean vorticity vector projected along the local mean velocity vector. It allows identifying the rotating direction of the coherent eddies. The well known vortical structures of the tip gap flow can be identified [36], namely the tip leakage vortex (TLV) which is the main highly coherent structure (in red) and the induced vortices (IV) that are counter rotating (in blue). The TLV is about the same shape and position in both simulations. It ap-

pears to be longer in the SBES visualization, due to the ability of the hybrid approach to resolve the structure on the coarsening grid. Finally, along the tip edge a separation (S) forms caused by the vena contracta effect of the leakage flow (LF) through the clearance, which is often referred to as a tip separation vortex. The LF forms elongated fingers that wraps around and eventually merge with the TLV. The structures are more clearly visible in the SBES approach because of both longer time averaging and higher dissipation properties of the numerical scheme.

3.2 Blade loading

To compare the cascade efficiency as predicted by the LES and the SBES at BEP, the pressure coefficient C_p , the friction coefficient C_f and the pressure fluctuation coefficient $C_{p,rms}$ have been calculated at mid-span $Y/C = 50\%$ and close to the tip $Y/C = 4\%$ (6.4 mm from the tip, 2.5% away from the tip). The comparison of the coefficients as a function of the dimensionless chordline coordinate x_c^* is given in Fig. 6. The square symbols represent the measurements performed by Staubs for the case of 1.6% gap and with vortex generator [37]. Blade loading, as illustrated by the pressure coefficient C_p , is quite similar for the two simulations, which agree well with the measurements [37]. Noticeably, the minimum location and amplitude of C_p along the suction at tip is very well captured in both simulations. Some differences can be noticed because of a different boundary layer transition in the different numerical approach. In the LES, on the suction side, the transition is forced by the trip which is noticeable by the strong fluctuations around $x_c^* = 0.1$ and $x_c^* = 0.15$; on the pressure side, the transition is triggered by a laminar separation bubble (LSB) noticeable by the negative double peaks between $x_c^* = 0.$ and $x_c^* = 0.1$. In the SBES, the suction side

FIGURE 6. MEAN PRESSURE, MEAN FRICTION AND PRESSURE FLUCTUATION COEFFICIENTS AT MID-SPAN (BOTTOM) AND 2.5% AWAY FROM THE TIP (TOP).

boundary layer is rapidly fully turbulent after $x_c^* = 0.1$ and shows higher friction coefficient values than in the LES. On the pressure side, the natural transition is somehow captured by the $k - \omega$ SST model [38], and the friction values are consequently similar to the LES. The differences in the turbulent development of the boundary layer on the suction side yield a mild flow separation in the aft portion of the blade, noticeable by the plateau in the pressure coefficient around $x_c^* = 0.9$, especially at mid-span. To differentiate between sides, the pressure fluctuation coefficient $C_{p,rms}$ is shown positive for the suction side and negative for the pressure side. The levels for the SBES are much smaller than in the LES. The levels increase along the chordline with development of the turbulent boundary layer, and higher levels along the suction side are measured close to the tip caused by the interactions with the tip gap. The pressure side transition is noticeable by the peak in $C_{p,rms}$ that corresponds to the locus of the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability induced by the LSB.

The pressure and friction forces have been integrated over the whole blade surface, and over only 20% of the blade span close to the tip. The lift and drag coefficients are reported in table 2. Consistently with the pressure and friction coefficient distributions analyzed previously in Fig. 6, the lift coefficient C_L in the LES is larger than in the SBES simulation, while the viscous drag coefficient $C_{D,v}$ is lower in the LES. The difference in pressure drag coefficient $C_{D,p}$ is consistent with the C_L differences between the 2 simulations. The differences in coefficients computed over the 20% tip section or the entire blade are small (about 2% reduction in lift and 2% increase in drag) showing that at the BEP, the tip gap flow influences the performance in a moderate manner.

TABLE 2. INTEGRATED LIFT AND DRAG COEFFICIENTS.

Name	LES-BEP	LES-BEP	SBES-BEP	SBES-BEP
Segment	blade	tip	blade	tip
C_L	0.541	0.528	0.498	0.489
$C_{D,p}$	0.063	0.064	0.053	0.055
$C_{D,v}$	0.004	0.005	0.007	0.008

3.3 Vortex and wake turbulence

To evaluate the quality of the simulations, the mean and root mean square of the velocity components are compared to experimental measurements taken in a cross-section plane of the cascade at $X/C_a = 1.37$ downstream [21]. In this plane, the TLV is still well resolved on the mesh grid.

In the LES simulations, the TLV has the right shape and location compared to experiments, while in the SBES, the TLV appears smaller and closer to the blade suction side. This deviation in the TLV trajectory was already observed in RANS simulations of the same configuration [39]. Looking at the Reynolds stress components, the LES lacks temporal statistical convergence, but provides the best agreement of the turbulent intensity components with experiments in terms of contour shape and extrema locations. On the contrary, the resolution of the wake is better achieved with the SBES. The hybrid approach is more robust in the non-uniform mesh regions.

FIGURE 7. MEAN STREAMWISE VELOCITY (TOP), TRACE COMPONENTS OF THE REYNOLDS STRESS: STREAMWISE, VERTICAL AND TRANSVERSE COMPONENT (FROM 2ND TO 4TH ROW) at $X/C_a = 1.37$.

3.4 Modal analysis

Figure 8 shows the energy distribution of the modes obtained with the SPOD decomposition for selected planes of analysis. Note that only the energy associated with the first mode is shown, as it is dominant over the higher order modes. The solid and dashed lines correspond to the SBES and LES results respectively. The LES results lack convergence and will be improved for the conference.

The eigenvalue spectra show similar broad bell shape in blade-to-blade and transverse planes for LES and SBES results. On the blade, the SBES eigenvalues are much smaller than the LES ones. This is consistent with the $C_{p,rms}$ observations which have demonstrated that the SBES resolves fluctuations only in the vicinity of the tip region. In the LES simulation, few humps emerge from the broadband levels. This is consistent with the DMD analysis performed by Koch *et al.* [16]. In the SBES spectra more humps are noticeable highlighting some amplification mechanisms that are not captured in the LES. The analysis will focus here on the common hump around 600 Hz and 1000 Hz. These mechanisms are related to both the tip gap flow as they emerge in the transverse planes, and the wake as they are clearly visible in the blade-to-blade at $Y/C = 50\%$.

FIGURE 8. SPOD EIGENVALUES AS A FUNCTION OF FREQUENCY FOR THE FIRST SPOD MODE, FOR SELECTED PLANE AT BEP.

Figure 9 shows a temporal reconstruction of the pressure field from the mode identified around 1000 Hz for the LES and SBES results. Three views of the same mode are presented: the blade-to-blade plane at $Y/C = 5\%$ in the tip gap flow area and the transverse planes at $x_c^* = 38\%$ and $x_c^* = 75\%$. The mode describes the rotating and wandering motion of the TLV which can be clearly identified in the top right corner in the transverse plane at $x_c^* = 75\%$. In the upstream plane at $x_c^* = 38\%$, no dynam-

ics are detected in the SBES results, while in the LES a strong shedding from the gap clearance can be noticed. In addition, the modal structures appear connected between the pressure and suction sides through the clearance in the LES results, while they are not in SBES. In the latter results, the vortex core is closer to the blade at $x_c^* = 75\%$ and is further downstream strongly interacting with the vortex shedding of the trailing edge in the plane $Y/C = 5\%$. In the LES results, the modal structure from the TLV vanishes passed the trailing edge without interacting with the trailing-edge vortex shedding.

FIGURE 9. VISUALIZATION OF SPOD MODE AT $f \approx 1000H_z$ FOR LES (TOP) AND SBES (BOTTOM) AT BEST EFFICIENCY POINT.

The tip gap is responsible for the unsteady dynamics of the flow in the cascade. In the SBES the TLV breakdown couple with the wake flow, while in the LES the energy is transferred towards smaller turbulent scales.

4 INFLUENCE OF OPERATING CONDITION ON TIP GAP FLOW

In this section, the results of the SBES simulations at the two operating conditions are briefly analyzed. The incoming flow is turned by 4° to define the Maximum Pressure Rise (MPR) operating condition. The change in flow structures in the tip gap region is clearly visible in the Fig. 10 showing the isosurface of $Q = 5 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-2}$. The boundary layers are still resolved in RANS

by the SBES hybrid approach, as no structures can be seen along the blade in ①. Consequently, the vortex shedding at the trailing edge in ② is still present. On the other hand, the development of the tip gap flow is strongly modified by the change in operating condition. Massive unsteady flow structure are increasing the blockage of the passage in ③, the incoming flow is deviated and perturbed by the unsteady tip leakage flow in ④ and large coherent pockets of turbulent eddies are shed along the pressure side of the blade and can be seen through transparency in ⑤.

FIGURE 10. INSTANTANEOUS VISUALIZATION USING AN ISOSURFACE OF Q CRITERION IN SBES SIMULATIONS AT BEP (TOP) AND MPR (BOTTOM).

The comparison of blade loading is given in Fig. 11 where the C_p distributions between the two operating conditions. The blade loading at MPR is significantly increased in particular close to the leading edge. The minimum of pressure coefficient is shifted from $x_c^* = 0.38$ at BEP to $x_c^* = 0.16$ at MPR. This location corresponds to the maximum leakage flow [36] and this can be clearly identified in Fig. 10 where the detachment of the TLV from the suction side is shifted from mid-chord in BEP towards almost the front of the tip edge.

Similarly to the BEP database, the temporal extractions at the selected locations shown in Fig. 3 are used to develop a modal analysis based on the SPOD. The eigenvalue spectra are presented in Fig. 12 and compared between BEP and MPR operating conditions. The dynamic response is clearly increased at MPR, demonstrating the unsteadiness of this operating condition. The frequency driving the dynamic is moved towards the low range,

FIGURE 11. MEAN PRESSURE COEFFICIENT AT MID-SPAN (BOTTOM) AND 2.5% AWAY FROM THE TIP (TOP) IN SBES SIMULATIONS AT BEP AND MPR OPERATING CONDITIONS.

in particular a peak emerges for all planes at $f = 180$ Hz, except in the mid-span section. The modal shape is represented in Fig. 13, which shows the temporal reconstruction of pressure in a blade-to-blade view and in a transverse plane.

The lobe distribution of the dominant frequency at MPR contrasts with the modal distribution analyzed previously at BEP in Fig. 9. The dominant amplitudes can be identified along the pressure side and convect from leading to trailing edges. The initial lobe formation close to the leading-edge is related to the TLV rotation that can be identified on the suction side by the long alternating strips. At this operating condition the two sides of the blade are connected in the passage through the blockage effect identified in Fig. 10 but also through the tip leakage. The main lobes on the pressure side enforce a pulsation of the tip leakage flow visible in the transverse plane at $x_c^* = 75\%$, which in turn enhances the wandering of the TLV. This particular mode demonstrates a natural feedback loop mechanism of the cascade flow which might be an inception mechanism of stall.

It will be interesting to further confirm this mechanism with the resolution and accuracy of the LES solver to capture the transition mechanism.

5 CASCADE NOISE

The power spectral density of the far-field noise at BEP can be obtained from the compressible LES with a Ffowcs Williams and Hawkins (FW-H) analogy that radiates the noise pressure

FIGURE 12. SPOD EIGENVALUES AS A FUNCTION OF FREQUENCY FOR THE FIRST SPOD MODE, FOR SELECTED PLANE WITH SBES AT BEP AND MPR.

fluctuations from the blade surface to the far field (for the solid surface formulation), or from a porous surface that records pressure, density, and velocity fluctuations (porous surface formulation). The latter is placed upstream of the cascade in order to capture the acoustic waves propagating through the cascade without any unsteady flow perturbations or spurious noise sources. The observer is located at 90° from the blade chord, at 1.2 m from the trailing edge, and at midspan on the suction side. The FW-H computation is achieved with the in-house code called *SherFWH* and is based on the advanced time approach for acoustic analogy predictions from Casalino [40]. The unsteady signals on the blade surface and the porous surface are recorded at a sam-

FIGURE 13. VISUALIZATION OF SPOD MODE AT $f \approx 180\text{Hz}$ FOR SBES AT MAXIMUM PRESSURE RISE CONDITION.

pling frequency of 60 kHz. The ambient medium is supposed at rest. Fig. 14 shows the resulting PSD obtained with Welch’s periodogram method [41], using 4 blocks with 50% overlap between each blocks for the averaging, which yields a frequency resolution of 88.9 Hz.

FIGURE 14. PSD OF FAR-FIELD ACOUSTIC PRESSURE FOR CASCADE WITH (LES-G) AND WITHOUT (LES-NG) TIP GAP AT BEP (BOTH SOLID AND POROUS FW-H).

Due to the lack of experimental acoustic results in such a linear cascade, the far-field PSD is compared with experimental data on the isolated CD airfoil at a similar angle-of-attack and Reynolds number [42, 43], and also with an analytical prediction with the extended Amiet’s model for an isolated airfoil [44–46]. The latter is based on the turbulent boundary layer statistics at midspan close to the trailing edge ($x/c_a = 0.9$). Both cascade results with gap (LES-G) yield larger levels than the no gap (LES-NG) cases, stressing the importance of the tip noise in this cascade even at BEP. All LES results yield similar levels as the

experimental ones up to 2 kHz, but the no-gap cases are significantly lower at mid to high frequencies. As already evidenced in [7], the porous surface FW-H spectra show troughs at frequencies $f_{c,i}$ corresponding to the cascade modes. Moreover, the solid FW-H spectra exhibit additional troughs at Helmholtz numbers based on the chord multiple of 2π , which match those of the analytical prediction with the extended Amiet’s model. In the latter, they are generated by the Fresnel functions and show the diffraction effect at the trailing edge when the blade chord is no longer compact.

FIGURE 15. COHERENCE BETWEEN THE LSB AND FAR-FIELD ACOUSTIC PRESSURES AT BEP.

Two extra humps with quasi-tonal peaks are seen in the spectra in the frequency range [3500,4000] Hz and [4500,10000] Hz respectively. To identify their origin, coherence of pressure fluctuations is calculated between wall-pressure sensors and the observer 1.2 m away from the blade. Note that the simulation signal length (45 ms) does not allow any statistical convergence below 1 kHz. In Fig. 15, the surface sensor is placed near the LSB identified on the blade pressure side. A clear high coherence is observed around 8 kHz, suggesting that the high-frequency hump is mostly caused by the LSB, which is consistent with what has been recently observed on the isolated CD airfoil at a similar Reynolds number [47,48]. In Fig. 16, the surface sensor is placed near the random tripping strip on the blade suction side. The high coherence peak at about 3500 Kz suggests that the mid-frequency humps is caused by the trip. Finally, the experimental spectrum on the isolated CD airfoil shows a plateau at high frequencies not clearly seen in the current cascade simulations: there is no clear evidence of the additional wake source in the LES results.

FIGURE 16. COHERENCE BETWEEN THE TRIP AND FAR-FIELD ACOUSTIC PRESSURES AT BEP.

6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The flow in a rectilinear compressor cascade with a tip has been investigated under two operating conditions using two solvers. First, the design operating condition, or Best Efficiency Point (BEP), was simulated using the incompressible Shear Blended Eddy Simulation (SBES) implemented in ANSYS CFX and with the compressible Large Eddy Simulation (LES) AVBP solver. These solvers accurately describe the aerodynamics, which is in agreement with published experimental measurements collected in the Virginia Tech (VT) Low Speed Wind Tunnel. Despite this similarity, the solvers demonstrate different dynamic responses when using Spectral Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (SPOD). In the hybrid RANS-LES SBES approach, the dominant dynamic mode shows a pairing of lobes between the tip leakage vortex (TLV) and the vortex shedding (VS) from the trailing-edge. At the same frequency, the LES simulation shows uncoupled modal structures between the VS and TLV, but coupling through the pressure and suction sides via the tip leakage flow. This difference may be due to the inherent switch between the LES and RANS resolution, which amplifies the natural instabilities in the SBES approach. A second operating condition, defined as the Maximum Pressure Rise (MPR) of the compressor cascade, has also been investigated using the same solvers. Unfortunately, due to a lack in convergence, only the SBES results have been analyzed and compared with the BEP. The increase in angle of attack of the incident flow causes an increase in loading, and shifts the TLV burst towards the blade leading-edge. SPOD analysis identifies a strong coupling between the pressure and suction sides of the blade via a traveling mode along the pressure side, which pumps energy from the TLV to the next blade passage via the tip leakage. Finally, the far-field

noise for the BEP has been computed using the compressible LES results using the Ffowcs Williams and Hawkins analogy in both its solid and porous formulations. Three main noise sources have been identified in the noise spectra. Thanks to the correlation between wall pressure probes and the far-field microphones, the transition mechanisms (tripping on the suction side and laminar separation bubble on the pressure side) can be distinguished as mid- and high-frequency noise sources. Comparing a similar cascade without a gap allows the identification of a significant tip gap noise contribution dominant around 1000 Hz, where the main SPOD mode emerges. Cascade cutoff frequencies have also been identified in the far-field noise spectrum. Non-compact diffraction humps at the trailing edge have also been evidenced. LES results at the MPR operating condition will further clarify the relationship between the acoustics and feedback loop mechanisms identified in the SBES case.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are thankful for the support from the NSERC grant RGPIN-2020-05919 and RGPIN-2019-05844. The simulations and their analysis were performed on the Niagara and Trillium supercomputer operated by SciNet as well as Narval supercomputer operated by Calcul Québec. These systems are offered and managed by the Digital Research Alliance of Canada. The authors want to thank the Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique (CERFACS), which develops and provides us with AVBP for academic research. Post-processing was enabled in part by means of the Antares Python API developed by CERFACS.

References

- [1] Storer, JA., and Cumpsty, NA., 1991. “Tip leakage flow in axial compressors”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **113**(2), pp. 252–259.
- [2] Denton, J. D., 1993. “Loss mechanisms in turbomachines”. In ASME 1993 International Gas Turbine and Aeroengine Congress and Exposition, American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
- [3] Kameier, F., and Neise, W., 1997. “Experimental study of tip clearance losses and noise in axial turbomachines and their reduction”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **119**(3), May, pp. 460–471.
- [4] Envia, E., 2017. “Noise emissions from commercial aircraft”. *Green Aviation—Reduction of Environmental Impact Through Aircraft Technology and Alternative Fuels*; Nelson, SE, Reddy, RD, Eds.
- [5] Stauter, RC., 1993. “Measurement of the three-dimensional tip region flow field in an axial compressor”. *Journal of turbomachinery*, **115**(3), pp. 468–476.
- [6] Tyacke, J., Vadlamani, NR., Trojak, W., Watson, R., Ma,

- Y., and Tucker, P.G., 2019. “Turbomachinery simulation challenges and the future”. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, p. 100554.
- [7] Koch, R., Sanjosé, M., and Moreau, S., 2021. “Large-eddy simulation of a single airfoil tip-leakage flow”. *AIAA Journal*, **0**(0), pp. 1–12.
- [8] Boudet, J., Caro, J., Li, B., Jondeau, E., and Jacob, M. C., 2016. “Zonal large-eddy simulation of a tip leakage flow”. *International Journal of Aeroacoustics*, **15**(6-7), pp. 646–661.
- [9] Mann, A., Kim, M.-S., Wu, J., Pérot, F., Grilliat, J., Jacob, M. C., and Colman, M., 2016. “Airfoil tip leakage aeroacoustics predictions using a lattice boltzmann based method”. In 22nd AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference, Lyon, France, June, AIAA-2016-2825.
- [10] Camussi, R., Grilliat, J., Caputi-Gennaro, G., and Jacob, M.C., 2010. “Experimental study of a tip leakage flow: Wavelet analysis of pressure fluctuations”. *Journal of fluid mechanics*, **660**, pp. 87–113.
- [11] Pérez Arroyo, C., Leonard, T., Sanjosé, M., Moreau, S., and Duchaine, F., 2019. “Large Eddy Simulation of a scale-model turbofan for fan noise source diagnostic”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **445**, pp. 64–76.
- [12] Kholodov, P., and Moreau, S., 2020. “Identification of noise sources in a realistic turbofan rotor using large eddy simulation”. *Acoustics*, **2**(3), pp. 691–706.
- [13] Hughes, C., Jeracki, R., Woodward, R., and Miller, C., 2002. “Fan noise source diagnostic test-rotor alone aerodynamic performance results”. In 8th AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference & Exhibit, p. 2426.
- [14] Woodward, R., Hughes, C., Jeracki, R., and Miller, C., 2002. “Fan noise source diagnostic test–far-field acoustic results”. In 8th AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference & Exhibit, p. 2427.
- [15] You, D., Wang, M., Moin, P., and Mittal, R., 2007. “Large-eddy simulation analysis of mechanisms for viscous losses in a turbomachinery tip-clearance flow”. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, **586**, pp. 177–204.
- [16] Koch, R., Sanjose, M., and Moreau, S., 2021. “Aerodynamic investigation of a linear cascade with tip gap using large-eddy simulation”. *Journal of the Global Power and Propulsion Society*, **5**, pp. 39–49.
- [17] Muthanna, C., and Devenport, W. J., 2004. “Wake of a compressor cascade with tip gap, part 1: Mean flow and turbulence structure”. *AIAA journal*, **42**(11), pp. 2320–2331.
- [18] Wang, Y., and Devenport, W. J., 2004. “Wake of a compressor cascade with tip gap, part 2: Effects of endwall motion”. *AIAA journal*, **42**(11), pp. 2332–2340.
- [19] Devenport, W. J., Wittmer, K. S., Muthanna, C., and Wenger, C. W., 2004. “Wake of a compressor cascade with tip gap, part 3: Two point statistics”. *AIAA journal*, **42**(11), pp. 2341–2346.
- [20] Becherucci, L., Koch, R., and Moreau, S., 2022. “Large-eddy simulation of a linear compressor cascade with tip flow: Effects of the moving endwall on the aerodynamics”. In Proceedings of Global Power and Propulsion Society, GPPS-TC-2022-102 Paper.
- [21] Muthanna, C., 1998. “Flowfield Downstream of a Compressor Cascade with Tip Leakage”. Master’s thesis, Virginia Tech, Nov.
- [22] Muthanna, C., and Devenport, W. J., 2004. “Wake of a Compressor Cascade with Tip Gap, Part 1: Mean Flow and Turbulence Structure”. *AIAA Journal*, **42**(11), Nov., pp. 2320–2331.
- [23] Wenger, C. W., Devenport, W. J., Wittmer, K. S., and Muthanna, C., 2004. “Wake of a Compressor Cascade with Tip Gap, Part 3: Two Point Statistics”. *AIAA Journal*, **42**(11), Nov., pp. 2341–2346.
- [24] You, D., Mittal, R., Wang, M., and Moin, P., 2004. “Computational methodology for large-eddy simulation of tip-clearance flows”. *AIAA journal*, **42**(2), pp. 271–279.
- [25] Menter, F., 2018. “Stress-Blended Eddy Simulation (SBES)—A New Paradigm in Hybrid RANS-LES Modeling”. In *Progress in Hybrid RANS-LES Modelling*, Y. Hoarau, S.-H. Peng, D. Schwaborn, and A. Revell, eds., Vol. 137. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 27–37.
- [26] Nicoud, F., and Ducros, F., 1999. “Subgrid-scale stress modelling based on the square of the velocity gradient tensor”. *Flow, turbulence and Combustion*, **62**(3), pp. 183–200.
- [27] ANSYS, Inc, 2022. CFX-Solver Theory Guide. Documentation 2022.R2, Canonsburg, PA, July.
- [28] Barth, T., and Jespersen, D., 1989. “The design and application of upwind schemes on unstructured meshes”. In 27th Aerospace Sciences Meeting, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics.
- [29] Schönfeld, T., and Rudgyard, M., 1999. “Steady and Unsteady Flow Simulations Using the Hybrid Flow Solver AVBP”. *AIAA Journal*, **37**(11), Nov., pp. 1378–1385.
- [30] Donea, J., 1984. “A Taylor–Galerkin method for convective transport problems”. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **20**(1), pp. 101–119.
- [31] Fosso Pouangué, A., Sanjosé, M., Moreau, S., Daviller, G., and Deniau, H., 2014. “Subsonic Jet Noise Simulations Using Both Structured and Unstructured Grids”. *AIAA Journal*, **53**(1), Dec., pp. 55–69.
- [32] Moreau, S., Henner, M., Iaccarino, G., Wang, M., and Roger, M., 2003. “Analysis of flow conditions in freejet experiments for studying airfoil self-noise”. *AIAA journal*, **41**(10), pp. 1895–1905.
- [33] Towne, A., Schmidt, O. T., and Colonius, T., 2018. “Spectral proper orthogonal decomposition and its relationship

- to dynamic mode decomposition and resolvent analysis”. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, **847**, July, pp. 821–867.
- [34] Schmidt, O. T., and Colonius, T., 2020. “Guide to Spectral Proper Orthogonal Decomposition”. *AIAA Journal*, **58**(3), Mar., pp. 1023–1033.
- [35] Sanjosé, M., and Drame, A., 2025. “Modal analysis of tip gap flow in a rectilinear cascade of compressor blades at off-design operating conditions”. In *Fan2025 International Conference on Fan Noise, Aerodynamics, Applications and Systems*.
- [36] Lakshminarayana, B., Zaccaria, M., and Marathe, B., 1995. “The Structure of Tip Clearance Flow in Axial Flow Compressors”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **117**(3), July, pp. 336–347.
- [37] Staubs, J. K., 2005. “Correlation between Unsteady Loading and Tip Gap Flow Occurring in a Linear Cascade with Simulated Stator-Rotor Interaction”. PhD thesis, Virginia Tech, May.
- [38] Menter, F., Hüppe, A., Matyushenko, A., and Kolmogorov, D., 2021. “An Overview of Hybrid RANS–LES Models Developed for Industrial CFD”. *Applied Sciences*, **11**(6), Jan., p. 2459.
- [39] Drame, A. B., and Sanjosé, M., 2024. “Analyse et modélisation des pertes dans une grille rectiligne de compresseur avec jeu”. *Transactions of the Canadian Society for Mechanical Engineering*, July.
- [40] Casalino, D., 2003. “An advanced time approach for acoustic analogy predictions”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **261**(4), pp. 583–612.
- [41] Welch, P., 1967. “The use of fast Fourier transform for the estimation of power spectra: A method based on time averaging over short, modified periodograms”. *IEEE Transactions on audio and electroacoustics*, **15**(2), pp. 70–73.
- [42] Jaiswal, P., 2020. “Experimental investigation of airfoil self-noise”. PhD thesis, Université de Sherbrooke.
- [43] Wu, H., Moreau, S., and Sandberg, R. D., 2020. “On the noise generated by a controlled-diffusion aerofoil at $Re=150,000$ ”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **487**, Nov., p. 115620.
- [44] Amiet, R. K., 1976. “Noise due to turbulent flow past a trailing edge”. *Journal of sound and vibration*, **47**(3), pp. 387–393.
- [45] Roger, M., and Moreau, S., 2005. “Back-scattering correction and further extensions of Amiet’s trailing-edge noise model. Part 1: Theory”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **286**(3), Sept., pp. 477–506.
- [46] Moreau, S., and Roger, M., 2009. “Back-scattering correction and further extensions of Amiet’s trailing-edge noise model. Part II: Application”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **323**(1), June, pp. 397–425.
- [47] Arroyo Ramo, A., Moreau, S., Sandberg, R. D., Bauerheim, M., and Jacob, M. C., 2025. “The effect of the leading-edge separation bubble vortex shedding on the far field noise of a Controlled Diffusion airfoil: A DNS study”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **618**, Dec., p. 119336.
- [48] Zhou, Z., Moreau, S., and Sanjosé, M., 2025. “Installation effects on airfoil self-noise estimated by direct numerical simulations”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **604**, May, p. 118978.